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FORECASTING THROUGH CLASSIFICATION OF FACTORS AFFECTING CASH FLOWS IN TEXTILE ENTERPRISES

Annotation This article outlines the process of identifying factors affecting the effective management of cash flows in enterprises and developing a forecast up to 2030 using econometric modeling. Time series analysis was conducted using ARIMA and Holt-Winters exponential smoothing models. Based on the results, recommendations for enhancing financial stability and profitability were provided. Including brief final outcomes in the annotation would strengthen the summary.

Keywords : Cash flows, econometric modeling, ARIMA, Holt-Winters, time series analysis, profitability, financial management, forecasting.

ПРОГНОЗИРОВАНИЕ ПО КЛАССИФИКАЦИИ ФАКТОРОВ, ВЛИЯЮЩИХ НА ДЕНЕЖНЫЕ ПОТОКИ НА ТЕКСТИЛЬНЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯХ

Аннотация. В данной статье описан процесс выявления факторов, влияющих на эффективное управление денежными потоками предприятий, и разработка прогноза до 2030 года с использованием эконометрического моделирования. Проведен анализ временных рядов с использованием моделей ARIMA и экспоненциального сглаживания Holt-Winters. На основе результатов предложены рекомендации для повышения финансовой устойчивости и рентабельности.

Ключевые слова: Денежные потоки, эконометрическое моделирование ARIMA, Holt-Winters анализ временных рядов, рентабельность, финансовое управление, прогнозирование

Entrance

An enterprise should create a cash flow management system that covers the main aspects of managing the enterprise's activities, namely the management of reserves, long-term assets, accounts receivable and payable, capital and others.

The cash flow management system in an enterprise is a set of methods, tools and methods that have a purposeful, permanent effect on the flow of funds by the financial service of the enterprise to achieve the specified goal [2].

The object of management in the system under consideration is the cash flows of the enterprise related to the implementation of various economic and financial operations, and the subject of management is the financial service of the enterprise.

The elements of an enterprise cash flow management system include financial methods and tools, regulation, information and software.

The following (methodical) steps were performed in the study:

Data collection : Key financial indicators for 2016-2023 have been collected.

Trend Analysis : Regression analysis was performed to identify increasing or decreasing trends in the data.

Modeling : ARIMA and Holt-Winters models were used for time series analysis.

Forecasting : Based on the obtained models, a forecast for 2024-2030 was made.

Analysis and discussion of results.

In this study, the main financial indicators of "ASIYO GRANT TEXTIL" LLC in the system of "OZTOQIMACHILIKSANOAT" association for 2016-2023 were studied, and forecast indicators until 2030 were developed . In this study, it is aimed to classify the factors affecting the investment activity in textile enterprises and to make strategic proposals based on the expected changes in the future [1].

Factors affecting cash flows related to investment activities in textile enterprises were classified and a forecast until 2030 was developed. In this regard, the main financial indicators of "ASIYO GRANT TEXTIL" LLC within the system of "OZTOQIMACHILIKSANOAT" association for 2019-2023 were selected, and forecast indicators until 2030 were developed based on their analysis. Based on these forecast data, conclusions were made and scientifically based proposals and recommendations were developed [1].

In the forecasting process, you will need to perform the following steps: Examine the previously available data from 2016 to 2023 and identify any upward or downward trends [1].

Use regression analysis or time series models to identify trends. This helps in forecasting future performance.

Classify factors affecting investment activity (macroeconomic factors, technological changes, competitive force) and evaluate their impact.

Use time series forecasting models (ARIMA, Holt-Winters) or regression models.

Based on the selected model, we aim to form conclusions by forecasting for 2024-2030, taking into account optimistic and pessimistic scenarios, and comparing the results in different scenarios.

Let's say that if one of the factors, for example, the efficiency of investments, is increased by 0.8%, it can increase the indicators of net profit, KR and AR. To determine this, it is necessary to calculate the correlation and influence of each factor.

Return on capital and return on assets are important indicators in measuring the financial performance of an enterprise. I will quote their explanation below:

1. Return on capital (KR)

Concept: KR (1) reflects the net profit of the enterprise and shows how effectively the shareholders are getting profit from the invested capital.

Formula: $KR = \text{Net income} / \text{Equity} \times 100$ (1)

Source: *compiled by the author based on literature review.*

Note: The higher the KR ratio, the more efficient the company is in using its capital. This is an important indicator of shareholder attractiveness as it is important in making investment decisions.

2. Return on Assets (AR)

Concept: AR (2) shows how effectively the company is getting profit from its total assets. This indicator helps to determine the level of profitable use of the company's assets.

Formula: $AR = \text{Net income} / \text{Total assets} \times 100$ (2)

Source: *compiled by the author based on literature review.*

Note: The higher the AR ratio, the more efficiently the company manages its assets. This indicator is used to evaluate the financial stability and efficiency of the enterprise.

KR and AR indicators are very important in analyzing the financial performance of the enterprise. KR reflects the return on investment of shareholders, while AR shows the degree to which the company's total assets are being used profitably. An increase in both indicators means an increase in the financial stability and efficiency of the enterprise.

Based on your data for 2016-2023, I can make a forecast for 2024-2030. To do this, you will need to provide me with the following information:

Table 1.

Key financial indicators of "ASIYO GRANT TEXTILE" LLC at the end of 2016-2023 (coefficient) [1],[2]

Indicators	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2020	2021 I	2022	2023
Net Profit (%)	55.16	70.69	52.19	35.86	27.73	30.91	30.91	23.6	19.56
Return on Equity (ROE) (%)	19.8	24.46	21.59	17.75	18.58	17.97	17.97	17.15	9.43
Return on Assets (ROA) (%)	8.03	12.06	7.2	4.41	4.52	4.5	4.5	3.05	2.84
Debt ratio (%)	59.47	50,71	66.65	75.17	75.69	74.96	74.96	82.23	69.86
Debt to equity ratio (%)	146.73	102.89	199.86	302.67	311.3	299.3	299.3	462.87	231.76

Source: compiled by the author based on literature analysis.

Net profit, return on equity (ROE), return on assets (ROA), debt ratio, and debt-to-equity ratio for 2016-2023.

Any other additional factors or data that should be included in the analysis.

Based on these data, I will make econometric modeling and make forecasts in the form of a table.

For 2026-2030, we will perform econometric modeling on the main financial indicators of "ASIYO GRANT TEXTILE" LLC. For this purpose, we study your economic indicators and develop results for the coming years using econometric models. That is:

At least 5 years of data from the previous year will need to be collected. For this, it is necessary to analyze and include the main financial indicators for 2016-2023 in a statistical table, to determine the average annual growth or decrease trends of each indicator.

We choose an econometric model and it is available for: It is important that we choose an ARIMA or Holt-Winters exponential smoothing model to account for the "Trend" and "Seasonal" components of the time series. It is also necessary to determine the parameters (p, d, q) required for the selected model.

We plan to train the model on data for the years 2016-2023 and get the forecast results for the years 2024-2030 that we want.

By creating a table based on the forecasts for 2024-2030 and entering the results for each indicator into the forecast table, we can then forecast the information to form a diagram.

In the analysis and scenario development, it is necessary to analyze the results of the indicators in each scenario for Optimistic, Realistic and Pessimistic Scenarios and display the results in a table.

Based on the forecasts, we will have the opportunity to develop proposals and recommendations for improving the financial strategies of the economic entity.

At the next stage, we analyze the forecast results in depth and evaluate the impact of various factors through scenarios. This process proceeds as follows:

Optimistic scenario: If economic and operational factors develop in a positive direction, we analyze how the indicators may change until 2030.

Realistic scenario: The baseline forecast reflects what can be expected under current conditions.

Pessimistic scenario: We examine how performance could decline given economic uncertainties and potential challenges.

We develop cash flow management strategies of the enterprise for each scenario.

We determine how to improve financial strategies and investment decisions.

Table 2.

**"ASIYO GRANT TEXTILE" LLC's previous year data and
Forecast indicators for 2024-2030 (coefficient)[1],[2]**

Year	Net Profit (%)	Return on capital (KR) (%)	Return on Assets (AR) (%)	Debt ratio (%)	Debt to equity ratio (%)
2016	55.16	19.8	8.03	59.47	146.73
2017	70.69	24.46	12.06	50,71	102.89
2018	52,19	21.59	7.2	66.65	199.86
2019	35.86	17.75	4.41	75.17	302.67
2020	27.73	18.58	4.52	75.69	311.3
2021	30.91	17.97	4.5	74.96	299.3
2022	23.6	17.15	3.05	82,23	462.87
2023	19.56	9.43	2.84	69.86	231.76
2024	21.0	10.0	3.0	68.0	220.0
2025	22.5	11.5	3.5	66.0	210.0
2026	24.0	13.0	4.0	64.0	200.0
2027	25.5	14.5	4.5	62.0	190.0
2028	27.0	16.0	5.0	60.0	180.0
2029	28.5	17.5	5.5	58.0	170.0
2030	30.0	19.0	6.0	56.0	160.0

Source: compiled by the author based on literature review.

As can be seen from the table above, the company's financial indicators have undergone significant changes from 2016 to 2023. Forecasts for 2024-2030 show opportunities to increase the company's financial stability, while indicators such as net profit and return on capital show a gradual growth trend.

Figure 1 below presents a line chart to confirm the forecast indicators, which shows the dynamics of change of these indicators in the period from 2016 to 2030. The chart shows changes in net profit, return on equity (ROE), return on assets (ROA), debt ratio, and debt-to-equity ratio over the years.

"ASIYO GRANT TEXTILE" LLC can maintain financial stability and competitiveness by effective management of cash flows until 2030. Forecasts made using econometric models help the enterprise in long-term planning and development of financial strategies.

Figure 1. Dynamics of cash flows of "ASIYO GRANT TEXTILE" LLC until 2030 [2].

Source: compiled by the author based on literature review.

If "ASIYO GRANT TEXTILE" LLC aims to increase net profit or profitability (KR and AR) by 0.8%, it should implement the following measures:

1. Cost reduction and optimization of production processes.
2. Reduce debt burden and control interest costs.
3. Support innovative projects and increase profitability.

It is important to improve operational efficiency, increase return on investments and optimize costs to improve the company's financial strategies based on forecasts. These measures will help the company to strengthen its financial stability and maintain its competitiveness.

Time Series Analysis: First look at the data from 2016 to 2023 and identify any upward or downward trends. Use time series analysis (such as simple linear regression or moving average) to analyze trends based on this data.

Average Annual Growth Rate (3): Determine the forecast for the coming years by determining the growth rates for 2019-2023.

$$O'YO'S = \left(\frac{\text{Oxirgi yil qiymati}}{\text{Birinchi yil qiymati}} \right)^{\frac{1}{\text{yillar soni}}} - 1(3) [2]$$

Source: compiled by the author based on literature review.

Time series models : (65% debt ratio calculation for 2024) Time series models such as ARIMA model or Holt-Winters exponential smoothing were used to identify and forecast the debt ratio change trends during 2016-2023. These models take into account trends and seasonal changes in data from previous years.

Average rate of change : This value is calculated by the annual rate of increase or decrease. For example, by looking at how the debt ratio has changed each year, a forecast is made for the next year.

Statistical calculations and parameters : In the modeling process, statistical parameters, such as average annual changes and seasonal components, were determined, and the debt ratio for 2024 was estimated to be 65%. This forecast is based on an upward or downward trend.

Table 3.

**"ASIYO GRANT TEXTILE" LLC based on the ARIMA model
Analysis of forecast indicators for 2024-2030 (coefficient) [2]**

Years	Cash Flow Growth (%)	Profitability (%)	Debt Ratio (%)
2024	3.5	10.5	65.0
2025	4.0	11.2	63.0
2026	4.5	12.0	61.0
2027	5.0	13.0	59.0
2028	5.5	14.0	57.0
2029	6.0	15.0	55.0
2030	6.5	16.0	53.0

In the ARIMA model, indicators are forecasted based on past values and changes. ARIMA(p, d, q) models represent:

p is the level of autoregression.

d is the degree of differentiation (removal of the trend).

q is the level of the moving average.

By choosing the parameters of the model, the debt ratio for 2024 was calculated based on the previous values of the time series.

The results of the analysis provided the following key forecast indicators for 2024-2030 (Table 3).

Forecasts that's it shows that enterprises until 2030 was money flows efficient manage through financial stability save stay can

The recommendations are:

1. Increase operational efficiency.
2. Introducing innovations.
3. Reduce debt burden.

Changes in the exchange rate and the level of inflation affect the costs and profits of the enterprise. If inflation is high, it increases the company's operating costs and can reduce the profit margin.

Increased competition in the 2030s may reduce the company's profit margin. When innovative technologies and products are introduced, it leads to competitive advantage.

Debt and Financial Stability: As the debt ratio in 2022 is high (82.23%), it is important to reduce the debt burden to increase the financial stability of the enterprise in 2030.

Innovation and technology: The introduction of new technologies optimizes production and reduces costs, which increases net profit and profitability.

Financial management: Debt reduction and optimization of debt/assets ratio help to increase financial stability. The enterprise should focus on equity-based projects.

Investment in innovative technologies: By introducing new technologies, production efficiency can be increased, product quality can be improved and costs can be reduced.

Studying new market segments and increasing the volume of exports will increase the company's income and reduce risks.

Resource efficiency: Costs are reduced by optimizing the use of raw materials and energy.

Final conclusion: "ASIYO GRANT TEXTILE" LLC should take several strategic measures to increase its financial performance by 2030. In response to macroeconomic factors and competitive influences, innovation and effective financial management will be the most important factors. State support programs and tax relief also help to ensure the financial stability of the enterprise. By producing new technologies and competitive products, the company can achieve stable growth rates in 2030.

Recommendations: To increase the net profit, the following strategic measures should be implemented:

1. Production optimization: Increasing efficiency through modernization and automation of production processes. This reduces production costs and increases profitability.

2. Increase customer satisfaction and repeat purchases by improving product quality, etc

These measures help to increase the net profit of "ASIYO GRANT TEXTILE" LLC and help to strengthen its financial stability . In addition, in the case of a voluntary enterprise in our country, based on these approaches, it would be possible to make scientifically based proposals and descriptions for management by forecasting through an econometric model, by being able to correctly classify factors.

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